

Conservation of Historic Buildings and their Adaptive Re-use

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Abstract

The change in usage pattern of the historic buildings has called for some serious structural interventions by means of additions and alterations during their repairs and maintenance etc. Past users have used and enjoyed these buildings in a very different way while the present users mostly intend to use these buildings with all available modern facilities like electrification, air conditioning even installation of passenger lifts etc. In some cases, the surface finishes are also altered as per the choice of the present users without caring for the compatibility of such alterations to an old building or the internationally accepted principles of conservation of historic buildings. As a result, conservation of these buildings has become more difficult and challenging. Historic buildings were constructed as per traditional building construction techniques and basic building materials were mostly locally sourced. But the present interventions and alterations are being done following modern building construction techniques and modern building materials which are adversely affecting the originality, authenticity, aesthetics and above all the structural stability of those historic buildings. Repair and maintenance of many such buildings are laid in the hands of modern engineers who are trying their best to add structural strength to these buildings by using modern materials and techniques. But, the use of such strong materials in old historic buildings which are made of comparatively softer and porous building materials in old days is resulting to irreparable damages. Conservation of the historic old buildings requires specialized skill. Understanding the building and its original construction technique etc is important before taking up any repair or maintenance work to these buildings. Alterations and additions should be sympathetic to the existing original building structure and the new building materials to be used for repair and maintenance should not be stronger than the materials used for original construction.

Key Words: Historic buildings, Conservation, Adaptive re-use

Introduction

Almost all the historic buildings in our country which are being re-used are built between eighteenth and early twentieth century. Basic construction materials of these buildings were mostly sourced locally and traditional building construction techniques were followed. Size, shape, access and facilities of these buildings were all designed according to the desire and also need of the original builders.

Usage pattern of almost all these heritage buildings which are being re-used has considerably changed over time. Take the example of a large three storied building designed in Italian style in Kolkata which was built in 1833 and was once used to accommodate one of the oldest Mercantile Banks is now accommodating permanent exhibition halls of art works in some portions of it and the other portions are accommodating some government offices. Similarly, a dwelling house of Rabindranath Tagore in Santiniketan which was built between 1858 and 1863 is now being used for exhibiting some paintings and photographs etc of those days to the visitors coming to Santiniketan. It is not very difficult to understand that most of the needs of the builders of these old buildings do not at all match with the needs of their present users.

As per the internationally accepted principles of conservation, originality, authenticity and integrity of the historic old buildings should be retained as far as possible with minimum changes and alterations. But the radical change in usage pattern of these buildings has called for some additions and alterations during their conservation and maintenance.

With the advent of new building materials and modern construction techniques, the traditional building materials as well as construction techniques used in historic buildings have now become obsolete. As a result, conservation and maintenance of the historic buildings for their continued performance have become more difficult and challenging to its present users. In fact, it required highly skilled experts and professionals for its proper upkeep. Detailed survey and investigation are necessary for understanding the original architectural details of the old buildings and their actual conservation needs for their prolonged usage and to satisfy the requirements of the present users. Proper maintenance and repair of these buildings require specialized skill. Conservation works are also required to be planned, estimated and supervised by expert engineer or architect having adequate experience in handling such works and the craftsmen deployed on conservation works should be used to working with traditional building materials and techniques.

Causes for Damage

Past users of many historic buildings had enjoyed the large airy and well-ventilated rooms with large window openings which were carefully designed for comfort of the users or dwellers of it. Besides for the user's comfort, these large window openings were also intended to effectively prevent dampness by evaporation of excess moisture from inside the massive masonry walls. But

the present uses of some of those buildings warranted the installation of air conditioners by permanently closing the large window openings perhaps mainly for the protection of the exhibits from dust, dirt and atmospheric moisture etc. In some cases, such serious structural alterations are also done to historic buildings for the comfort of its present users.

This particular action considerably hampered the original ventilation system of these buildings and serious dampness problems are invited. Such structural interventions within the original settings of the historic buildings are critical. It has the following risks involved;

- Some structural damages to the historic building fabrics are unavoidable during installation of air conditioners and providing necessary electric connections to those.
- It is not always possible to completely hide such installations. As a result, these additions and alterations adversely affect the original look of the interiors of the historic buildings.
- As a result of permanently closing the original window openings, the process of ventilation and extraction of excess moisture from the huge masonry walls by evaporation, which was the intension of the original builder for good health of the structure, is compromised and the building starts suffering from dampness.

Besides air conditioning, many more additions and alterations are to be done to historic old buildings for their adaptive re-use like high-capacity water tanks are placed on the old roofs and water pipes are laid indiscriminately to cater the growing need of water for the present users of many historic buildings. Also electrical cables and wires are laid over roofs and wirings done on historic wall surfaces and roofs

This not only causes structural damages to the old roofs but also causes stagnation of rainwater over the roof by preventing easy flow of rain water towards the carefully designed old spouts. This particular problem has seriously damaged the roofs of many ancient buildings and also monuments in the country. There are instances of relaying the original old floor of historic buildings by replacing old porous floor slabs by impermeable modern floor tiles. By doing so the permeability through the porous floor slabs which was the intention of the original builder for maintaining the floor free from damp, is compromised and serious dampness problem occurred causing damages to the floor and to the objects kept on it.

While planning for restoration or conservation of a traditionally constructed old building for its adoptive re-use, it is to be kept in mind that conservation of historic old building is not a one-time exercise but a continuous process. It is a preservative science and the efficacy of a good conservation work depends on the appropriate implementation of a well drawn maintenance protocol specific to the building and its present uses. Therefore, doing some good repair works to a traditionally constructed old masonry building does not guarantee for its desired performance as is expected from a modern building unless followed by regular maintenance. On the contrary,

such occasional repair adopting whatever good techniques and materials used, if not followed by a well-drawn maintenance plan (SOP) it is bound to produce frustrating results and even can lead to accelerated decay and damages to the building.

In order to draw an appropriate conservation plan for an old historic building under re-use, the entire building should be surveyed. The signs of distress or damages like dampness etc appeared in one corner of a building may be the resultant effect of a major structural defect developed on the opposite corner of it. If these signs of damages are only repaired without caring for their sources then the actual problem remains unseen and unattended which continues damaging the other portions of the building. We don't see them until those become serious and appear before us in the forms of cracks or peeling off or even partial collapse. So, carrying out some repair works to the damaged or distressed portion alone does not solve the structural problem rather makes it more critical and complicated.

Experience shows that most of the visible damages and distress in an old masonry building are the results of inappropriate repair and maintenance to it for years together either by its present users or by the present owner of it. It is also observed that while repairing an old building for re-use, more attention is paid to make it modern and scraping its old utility systems by introducing modern facilities and at the same time beautification of its interiors and exterior facades.

By and large, very less or no attention is paid to matching the repair works with the original as per the maintenance protocol of old and historic buildings. The present user is happy to see the beautiful building he uses compromising with the norms which kept the original building heal and hearty for years together.

Figures 1 and 2 show that the roof of a century old masonry building has been covered with bituminous sheets in order to prevent ingress of rain water through the old leaky roof.

Figure 1

Figure 2

An old roof surface of a heritage building is covered with bituminous felt for water tightening

Concerned engineer or the owner of the property ordered for covering the entire lime concrete roof with bituminous felt as per maintenance protocol of modern buildings without considering the probable interactions between century old lime concrete surface and the bituminous felt spread over it. As a result, rainwater started entering through many more locations of the roof, got trapped in between roof surface and tar felt and the trapped water caused damages to adjoining masonry by developing cracks, rusting to embedded and supporting iron members of roof and cracking the old masonry walls etc (fig 3, 4 and 5). Thus, an inappropriate repair work to an old masonry building accelerated the damages more than it was anticipated.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

The inappropriate action of water tightening has resulted to damages to the old masonry walls and roof by trapping of moisture

Dampness is a very common conservation issue observed in almost every old masonry building particularly those which are under re-use. Before jumping upon an easy and quick fix solution to this problem it is important to understand why this building has started suffering from so much of dampness which has so beautifully performed for last so many decades.

If we first understand the building by close inspection and then properly scrutinize the records of repairs and maintenance of it for last 10-15 years, it will certainly arrive at a conclusion that “wrong maintenance and developmental works to this building and its surroundings are chiefly responsible for inviting dampness problem to this old building”.

While taking up maintenance and developmental works to an old building, attention should be paid to retain the existing original drainage system all around the building. In many cases number of wash rooms are increased or capacity of existing washrooms are enhanced in a historic building to match the needs of its present uses but the water drainage system is not improved rather jeopardized. The outcome is stagnation of water along outer periphery of the building and soaking of water by the bottom portions of the old masonry walls. Rain water pipes and their joineries are also not well maintained in many old buildings in use, causing ingress of water into the old masonry (fig 6).

Figure 6 Existing old surface drainage system of the heritage building has disappeared and indiscriminate laying of rain water pipes etc have caused dampness into the old masonry walls

Thick masonry walls of these buildings allow entry and migration of water inside those much more than into the thin walls of modern buildings for the reason that old walls were constructed using porous lime mortar in old days while the modern walls are constructed using less porous and more rigid cement mortar. Hence, attention should be paid to retain the original pore

structures of the plasters and other surface finishes like colour washes etc to retain permeability of the old historic wall surfaces to avoid dampness. A deviation from this is bound to invite serious dampness problem to old buildings which are neither provided with damp proofing course at their plinth level nor are built in impermeable or less permeable materials like cement etc.

Conclusion

Keeping in view of the above facts, the custodians or owners of historic buildings should undertake periodic inspection to their properties by experienced engineer or architect having good knowledge of old building construction and uses of traditional building materials. The chief aim of such inspection is to examine the state of dilapidation of different portions of the building as well as to keep vigil on effects of the structural interventions, if anything is done to the historic building fabrics. Necessary repairs or alterations should be done using compatible materials which match the composition and strength of the existing original building fabrics as far as possible. Finally, for the sake of conservation of historic buildings, the extent of structural interventions aimed at to satisfy the needs of its present users should be kept as minimum as possible.

